

The range of sight over the horizon

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Every observer has noticed that we can see farther on a tower or a mountain than on the plane or in a valley. We want to work with the range of sight e with that we can still recognize an object with the height d . The observer stands on a tower or a mountain with the height h .

r is the earth's radius respectively the planet's radius

From the figure we take the following equations:

$$e = \frac{\alpha}{360^\circ} \cdot 2\pi r \quad \alpha \text{ in degree}$$

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{r}{r+h} + \arccos \frac{r}{r+d}$$

Both equations composed yields:

$$e = \frac{\pi r}{180^\circ} \cdot \left(\arccos \frac{r}{r+h} + \arccos \frac{r}{r+d} \right)$$

In circular measure:

$$e = r \cdot \left(\arccos \frac{r}{r+h} + \arccos \frac{r}{r+d} \right) \quad (1)$$

Thus we have found a formula for the range of sight. In the special case $d = 0$ we obtain the formula for the horizon range of sight. We get then:

$$e = r \cdot \arccos \frac{r}{r+h} \quad (2)$$

From the figure we see that in case $h, e \ll r$ the Pythagoras theorem is valid:

$$(r+h)^2 \approx r^2 + e^2$$

Multiplying out:

$$h^2 + 2rh \approx e^2$$

It follows:

$$e \approx \sqrt{h^2 + 2rh} \approx \sqrt{2rh} \quad \text{because of } h^2 \ll 2rh$$

This approximation can be transformed to:

$$h \approx \frac{e^2}{2r} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad r \approx \frac{e^2}{2h}$$

These formulas are all valid for $h, e \ll r$. Now we turn again to equation (1). We define:

$$\begin{aligned} a &:= \frac{r}{d+r} & ad + ar &= r \\ \Rightarrow d &= \frac{r \cdot (1-a)}{a} = r \cdot \left(\frac{1}{a} - 1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

Now we can solve easily the equation (1) to d , if we insert for a the term:

$$a = \cos \left(\frac{e}{r} - \arccos \frac{r}{r+h} \right)$$

We obtain:

$$d = r \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\cos \left(\frac{e}{r} - \arccos \frac{r}{r+h} \right)} - 1 \right)$$

or to h with cyclic permutation:

$$h = r \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\cos \left(\frac{e}{r} - \arccos \frac{r}{r+d} \right)} - 1 \right)$$

The sight can be obstructed if there is an object, for example a tower or a mountain, on a place between d and h that has a larger height than that for this place calculated d .

Now we ask the question which area under the same conditions can be surveyed through an observer?

We have again the equation:

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{r}{r+h} + \arccos \frac{r}{r+d}$$

and

$$h_k = r \cdot \cos(180^\circ - \alpha) + r$$

With $\cos(180^\circ - \alpha) = -\cos \alpha$ we get:

$$h_k = r \cdot (1 - \cos \alpha)$$

Now we insert for α :

$$h_k = r \cdot \left(1 - \cos \left(\arccos \frac{r}{r+h} + \arccos \frac{r}{r+d} \right) \right)$$

or with the addition theorem $\cos(a+b) = \cos a \cos b - \sin a \sin b$
and $\sin a = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 a}$:

$$h_k = r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{r^2 - \sqrt{(2rh + h^2) \cdot (2rd + d^2)}}{(r+h) \cdot (r+d)} \right)$$

The belonging surface of the spherical layer is:

$$A = 2\pi r \cdot h_k$$

This is searched area. At $d = 0$ it follows the simple sight area until the horizon:

$$A = \frac{2\pi r^2 h}{r+h} \quad \text{because of} \quad h_k = \frac{rh}{r+h}$$

In the case $h \gg r$ is $A \approx 2\pi r^2$, then it's possible to survey the half surface of the ball (the planet).

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001